

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Cyclic Alcohols by Bromamine-T in Acidic Media

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The oxidation of cyclopentanol and cyclohexanol by Bromamine-T (BAT) has been studied in perchloric acid. The main product of the oxidation is the corresponding ketone. The reaction is first order in alcohol, BAT and H^+ . Zero effect of ionic strength of the medium and *p*-toluenesulphonamide was observed. The rates were determined at four temperature, and activation parameters were evaluated. A solvent isotope effect ($k_1 D_2O/k_1 H_2O = 2.35-2.64$ and $2.39-2.72$ for cyclopentanol and cyclohexanol, respectively) has been observed at 35° . A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion to the oxidant has been suggested.

N-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE (NBS), *N*-bromoacetamide (NBA), Chloramine-T (CAT), Chloramine-B (CAB) and *N*-chlorosuccinimide are well known organic positive halogen compounds and several reports have appeared on the mechanism of their reactions¹⁻⁸. Another compound of this category is sodium *N*-bromotoluenesulphonamide (Bromamine-T or BAT). Not much information is available on the mechanism of oxidation by BAT except in Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of some alcohols^{9,10} by BAT, and thus there is no other report in the literature about its mode of oxidation for uncatalysed reactions involving BAT as oxidant. This prompted us to undertake this investigation.

Experimental

BAT solution was prepared and standardised by the method described in the previous paper⁹. Both the alcohols were commercial (E. Merck) products. CAT (E. Merck, p.a.), *p*-toluenesulphonamide (TSA) (Koch-light, England) and perchloric acid (E. Merck) samples were used. All other chemicals were of analytical grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the course of investigations.

The kinetic procedure employed was the same as reported in the previous communication⁹. The kinetics was followed by estimating the remaining [BAT] iodometrically at different time intervals. The reactions were followed upto 75% and duplicate kinetic runs showed that the results are reproducible within $\pm 2.6\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: Various sets of experiments were carried out with varying ratios of BAT-alcohol. The excess of BAT left in each set was estimated. These studies showed that one mole of alcohol consumed one mole of BAT and accordingly the following stoichiometric equation could be formulated, where R represents

$-CH_2-$ and $-(CH_2)_2-$ groups in cyclopentanol and cyclohexanol, respectively.

The end products, corresponding ketones were identified by conventional spot test analysis¹¹ and also through dinitrophenyl hydrazine (DNP) derivative¹².

Results and Discussion

The first order dependence on BAT was established by effecting a manifold variation in the [BAT] at 35° (Table 1). The reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to each alcohol and H^+ , which was obvious from nearly one slope value of the straight lines obtained from $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{Alcohol}]$ plots (Fig. 1, A and B) and $\log k_1$ vs $\log [H^+]$ plots (Fig. 1, C and D). Negligible effect of ionic strength (affected by addition of different amounts of NaClO_4) and TSA variations were observed (Table 1). Zero effect of TSA on reaction rate suggests that the post-equilibrium step involves a process in which TSA is one of reaction products (equilibrium 3). Table 1 includes the kinetic data at 30, 35, 40 and 45° , and also the values of energy of activation (ΔE) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger). The effect of solvent composition (acetic acid- H_2O in different ratios) and solvent isotope (D_2O - H_2O in different ratios) was studied and the results are recorded in Table 2.

The reaction is not affected by added radical scavengers, like allyl acetate as allyl acetate, upto 0.02 M did not affect the oxidation rate.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [OXIDANT], [TSA], IONIC STRENGTH (μ) AND TEMP. ON REACTION RATE

Temp. = 35° (unless otherwise mentioned)

[BAT] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ ^{**} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₁ ^{**} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0.40	19.12	19.81
0.50	19.16	—
0.67	19.15	19.79
1.00	19.00	19.84
1.25	19.12	19.84
1.43	—	19.85
2.00	19.11	19.77
2.50	19.14	19.82
1.00	19.02 ^a	19.86 ^a
1.00	19.06 ^b	19.80 ^b
1.00	19.03 ^c	19.84 ^c
2.00	19.16 ^d	19.78 ^d
2.00	19.20 ^e	19.80 ^e
2.00	19.12 ^f	19.76 ^f
1.00	12.36 ^g	13.44 ^g
1.00	25.94 ^h	29.09 ^h
1.00	38.30 ⁱ	29.04 ⁱ

*[Cyclopentanol] = 2.00 × 10⁻³ and [HClO₄] = 2.00 × 10⁻³ M.
 **[Cyclohexanol] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ and [HClO₄] = 0.50 × 10⁻³ M.
^a 0.50, ^b 1.00 and ^c 2.00 × 10⁻³ M [TSA]; ^d 0.05, ^e 0.075, ^f 0.15, ^j 0.075 × 10⁻¹, ^k 0.10 × 10⁻¹, and ^l 0.25 × 10⁻¹ M μ ;
^g 30, ^h 40 and ⁱ 45° temp.
 $\Delta E = 12.20$ and 10.98 kcal mol⁻¹, $\Delta S = -12.18$ and -11.94 e.u. for oxidation of cyclopentanol and cyclohexanol, respectively.

Fig. 1. (A) Plot of log k₁ vs log [cyclopentanol] at [HClO₄] = 2.00 × 10⁻³ M;
 (B) Plot of log k₁ vs log [cyclohexanol] at [HClO₄] = 0.50 × 10⁻³ M,
 (C) Plot of log k₁ vs log [H⁺] at [cyclopentanol] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ M, and
 (D) Plot of log k₁ vs log [H⁺] at [cyclohexanol] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M; [BAT] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, temp. 35°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION AND SOLVENT ISOTOPE ON REACTION RATE

Temp. = 35°

[BAT] = 2.00 × 10⁻³ M; [HClO₄] = 0.05 × 10⁻³ M

AcOH-H ₂ O %, v/v	k ₁ ^{**} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₁ ^{**} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	D ₂ O-H ₂ O %, v/v	k ₁ ^{**} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₁ ^{**} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0-100	2.40	19.77	0-100	2.40	19.77
20-80	3.58	30.12	30-70	5.64	47.28
35-65	4.92	40.82	50-50	6.02	51.40
50-50	6.12	50.16	70-30	6.34	53.77
60-40	7.41	61.18	—	—	—

* [Cyclopentanol] = ** [Cyclohexanol] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M.

Assuming BAT behaves like CAT, the following equilibria⁹ are possible in acidified BAT solution (where Ts = CH₃C₆H₄SO₃).

The probable oxidising species are TsNHBr, TsNBr₂ and HOBr. It has been reported by Soper¹³ that [HOCl] is very small in acidified CAT and is independent of [CAT]. Similar conclusion may also be drawn for [HOBr] in acidified solution of BAT and thus any role of HOBr as an oxidant is unlikely. Dibromamine-T (TsNBr₂) may be ruled out as the reactive species in view of the strict first

order dependence on BAT. Further, zero effect of TSA on the reaction rate precludes both TsNBr₂ and HOBr as the real oxidising species. The only choice left is to assume TsNHBr as the real and the most predominant oxidising species in our case. Such species has also been reported earlier by Singh *et al.*⁹

The increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solution decreases the polarity of the solvent and favours the process producing uncharged molecules from ions¹⁴. Therefore, the equilibrium (2) is favoured by solvent with increasing amounts of acetic acid which may explain the observed increase in the rate.

Based on the above statements and experimental findings, the following mechanism involving a hydride ion transfer from alcohol to the oxidant is

suggested (where, R is $-\text{CH}_2-$ and $-(\text{CH}_2)_2-$ for cyclopentanol and cyclohexanol, respectively).

The following rate equation may be derived for the above mechanisms in terms of consumption of [BAT].

$$-\frac{d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = k^* [\text{TsNHBr}] [\text{Cyclic alcohol}] \quad (6)$$

$$= k_s K [\text{TsNBr}^-] [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] [\text{Cyclic alcohol}] \quad (7)$$

The rate law (equation 7) shows first order dependence on BAT, H^+ and cyclic alcohols. Substantial deuterium isotope effect is also in excellent agreement with carbonium ion character in the transition state. A hydride ion transfer from

alcohol molecule to the oxidant in the rate determining step, further eliminates the scope of a hydrogen abstraction mechanism in the present investigation, which is supported by zero effect of radical scavenger.

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